

Super Conducting Wind Turbine

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Introduction

- The goals for the European Union:
- The EU's overall 20% renewable energy target for 2020 has been divided into legally binding targets for the 27 Member States, averaging out at 20%. [1]
 - In terms of electricity consumption, renewables should provide about 35% of the EU's power by 2020. [1]
 - By 2020, wind energy is set to contribute the most - nearly 35% of all the power coming from renewables. [1]

Off shore production 2008:

- 1.4 GW (2%)
- 626 turbines
- 2.3 MW average

Goals for off shore production 2030:

- 120 GW (Roughly 50%)
- 12000 turbines (10 MW turbines)

The technology trend is leading towards direct driven turbines, advantages:

- Low maintenance

Disadvantages:

- Larger generators (low speed/high torque)

Large generators increases the overall cost of the turbine due to extra materials and logistics, but save money on fewer foundations.

The size can be reduced by use of permanent magnets which is a method presently used. Further reduction of generator size could be done by use of superconductor.

This project concerns an investigation in the use of superconductors in future wind turbine generators.

1 - The European Wind Energy Association

It is important to keep the flux density in the iron below a certain level to avoid high losses compromising the generators efficiency. It is also vital not to use too much iron resulting in a heavy and costly generator. When designing the generator several simplifying assumptions are made while working in Matlab. When a design is complete it is simulated by using finite element method in Infolytica Magnet in order to correct for these assumptions. The depiction above shows the flux density in a pole of a 3 MW generator. The flux density is within the required limits.

Introduction

Why? The reason to use super conductors in wind turbines is that they have a resistance of almost 0Ω at low temperatures. This means they have lower power dissipation and thereby a higher current density which reduces the size and weight of the wind turbine generator. The loss reduction due to superconductors improves the efficiency of the wind turbine at all operation speeds.

Small Scale Generator

Process? In order to test the behavior of a generator with super conductive wire a small scale model has been built and tested

The blue line shows the flux density [B] as a function of current in the superconductor. It is seen that when increasing the current the flux density will also increase.

The red line shows that with increasing current the flux density has to be reduced to maintain the super conducting properties. From the curves it can be concluded that the superconductor is able to reach a maximum of 75A.

The red line shows the air gap flux density at room temperature. The superconductor acts as a normal copper conductor giving a maximum current of 1A. The maximum air gap flux generated at 1A is 18mT. The blue line shows the air gap flux density at 50A and with the temperature at 77 K. At this state a much higher air gap flux density can be obtained.

$$T = (B \cdot i \cdot l) \cdot r$$

Due to the higher flux density (B) and higher current (i) the torque increases.

The red line shows the torque at room temperature with one amp.

The blue line shows the torque at 50A and at a temperature of 77 K. The torque is increased by a factor of 10 by using superconductors.

Conclusion

In this project we have investigated the feasibility of using type II high temperature superconductors in electric generators of future off shore wind turbines. High temperature superconductors can be used to generate a considerable higher magnetic field than in classical magnet designs and thereby reduce weight. The purpose was to assess the technical and economical feasibility of using superconducting generators for offshore wind turbines producing 10-20 MW.

It was found that by designing a superconducting generator the weight of the generator can be reduced by approximately 90 ton. Before this becomes economically feasible the price of the super conducting material needs to decrease significantly